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HR service of a modern educational organization in the context of global digitalization: development strategy

KEYWORDS

HR service center,
HR service of a modern educational organization,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. In the modern world, much attention is paid to a systematic approach to human capital, without which it is impossible to implement any plans to increase the competitiveness, innovation and efficiency of any organization. Global changes are currently taking place in the education system. The transformation of the HR service comes to the fore, responsible for creating a cohesive team with a harmonious socio-psychological climate, preparing all the conditions for making personnel decisions that satisfy everyone: both the management of the educational organization and the entire teaching staff. The study aims to identify the development strategy of the HR service of a modern educational organization in the context of global digitalization.

Materials and Methods. General and special methods of scientific knowledge were applied: systemic, structural, and functional analysis, expert assessments, comparison, identification of the personal and activity characteristics of an effective HR manager, generalization of his functions. A systematic analysis of research literature allowed determining the development strategy for the HR service of an educational organization and outline prospects.

Results and discussion. The practice of managing educational organizations faces a significant change in the general paradigm of management. Today, pedagogical workers are considered as the main resource that largely determines the success of all its activities and needs to be properly managed and create optimal conditions for development. The emphasis is on studying the features of the HR service of a modern educational organization, the methods used by it in the war for talents. It is substantiated that talented employees determine the success of the entire organization, and an organization that works tirelessly to find, attract, retain, adapt, motivate and continuously develop talents will be more competitive. The main personal and activity characteristics of HR managers in the context of global digitalization are revealed. Strategies for the development of the HR service of an educational organization are identified. Recommendations are presented in the development of the HR service of an educational organization at the present stage.

Conclusion. The study allowed concluding that it is necessary to transform the HR service of an educational organization, strengthen its role in the management of teaching staff, create optimal conditions for their development and include it in the war for talents in order to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the organization. The HR service of an educational organization should become the main structure and an active tool for personnel management. In view of the clear trend towards the reduction of talented people, HR managers should be more actively involved in finding, attracting, retaining, adapting, mentoring and developing talent, at the same time skillfully using modern methods and technologies, including digital ones, at all stages of management.

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INTRODUCTION

Digitalization intensively entered all spheres of human activity from economics to management, from technology to medicine, from science to education. This became especially evident during the COVID-2019 pandemic, when educational organizations around the world were forced to switch to distance learning.

“Digitalization is nothing more than a special (digital) way of encoding information, and this is a method that allows you to tremendously increase the speed of information dissemination, creates fundamentally new opportunities for processing its huge arrays” [1, p. 18]. Various researchers and scientists believe that countries that are ready for the global digitalization of all sectors of life in the near future will become world leaders.

The Federal project “Digital educational environment” [2] (implementation period 01/01/2019-12/30/2024) is aimed to create and implement a digital educational environment in educational organizations and ensure digital transformation of the education system; the cost is estimated at 73.4 billion RUR.

Modernization of domestic education and its competitiveness in the world market of educational services within the framework of global digitalization and of digital economy is impossible without a systematic approach to developing the HR service of an educational organization, without solving the problems of attracting and retaining talented teachers and management personnel.

The HR service brings together specialists in the field of personnel management of an organization and everything related to it, and performs such functions as hiring, administration, creating conditions, adaptation, training, development, motivation, remuneration, assessment, HR branding, etc. At the same time, the development strategy of the HR service of educational organizations is to aim for active involvement in the “war” for talented teachers. After all, the total number of talents will determine the efficiency and competitiveness of an educational organization in the market of educational services at present. This study focuses on methods and technologies for attracting and retaining talents.

The opportunity for professional development of teaching staff and improvement of their qualifications under additional professional programs from the federal register, as part of the functionality of the HR service, is enshrined in two Russian projects (implementation period 01/01/2019-12/31/2024): the Federal project “Modern School” [3] and the National Project “Education” [4]. Thus, according to the plan of the latter, by the end of 2024, more than 40% of teachers will improve their skills.

“Digitalization brings many benefits, solves many problems but can also create threats to the very existence of a person. And this means that the projects proposed as part of digitalization need serious philosophical expertise aimed to humanize information technologies and cultivate the highest human values: freedom, personal autonomy, dignity, identity, creativity, understanding, and mutual understanding. Philosophy is most in demand during periods of cultural and cognitive crises. We are experiencing just such a time” [1, p. 29].

The study aims to identify the development strategy of the HR service of a modern educational organization in the context of global digitalization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the study, general and special methods of scientific knowledge were applied: systemic, structural and functional analysis, expert assessments, comparison, identification of the personal and activity characteristics of an effective HR manager, generalization of their functions. A systematic analysis of research literature allowed determining the development strategy for the HR service of an educational organization and outline prospects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In Russia in the 1990s, with realization of the importance the human factor carries for the organization’s efficiency, the personnel department gradually began to be replaced by a multifunctional HR service which allows performing such diverse functions as “staff planning, recruitment and selection of personnel, adaptation, training and development of personnel, service and professional promotion of personnel, organization of labor in the workplace, corporate culture management, motivation and remuneration of personnel, controlling and personnel assessment, personnel marketing, information support and organization of personnel management” [5, p. 2].

According to researchers, in the modern world, HR services play a special role not just as administrators but as strategic partners, which is directly related to the awareness of business efficiency and personnel management [6, p. 239]. In this regard, small and medium-sized enterprises in the service and manufacturing sector face certain difficulties in the strategic skills of personnel management in the context of the deployment of strategic and IT capabilities [7].

The HR service appearing in educational organizations almost marked a “revolution” in personnel management.

Today, teaching staff are considered as the main resource of an educational organization, determining the success of all its activities, which is to be competently managed and optimal conditions for its development are to be created [8]. Thus, managers of the HR service are called upon to co-manage this resource together with the heads of the educational organization.

An effective HR manager, in addition to knowledge about the features of the professional activities of the organization, is to have certain personal and activity characteristics that allow successfully performing functions. “They are to be sociable, focused on success, self-confident and stress-resistant. Such person adequately perceives criticism, tries to benefit from it and eliminate the shortcomings, and takes active measures for improvement. Moreover, the HR manager is to have an active life position, be able to easily adapt to rapidly changing conditions, provide competent assistance in non-standard situations, have analytical thinking and organizational skills” [6, p. 239].

Every day, new functions appear in the activities of an HR manager. In addition to search and attraction, there is a trend “in personnel management, indicated by leading Russian scientists, taking into account the emphasis on talents” [9, 269]. It is necessary to constantly expand the list of services in relation to talent management and improve their quality (increase competence and work on their effectiveness, provide continuing education, etc.) [10].

Despite the fact that Russia has one of the lowest unemployment rates in the world at 5.5%, and in Moscow and St. Petersburg this level is less than 2%, our labor market is not attractive enough for the most talented workers – “bearers of the universal competencies of the 21st century”. In the annual Global Talent Competitiveness Index (GTCI) in 2017, Russia ranked 56th out of 118 participating countries. “At the same time, according to the “Attractiveness” criterion, the country took only 81st place, and even 107th in terms of creating opportunities for talents” [11].

In this regard, the HR service of an educational organization is to become a fundamental management structure that allows achieving the global goals of the organization and work towards realizing its mission. The HR service is to become a forge of talents – “the higher the creative activity and initiative of employees, the higher the efficiency and competitiveness of the educational institution” [12]. Therefore, in order to attract talented teachers to educational organizations, an HR manager is to know all the nuances of the war for talents, master the most successful management tools, including benchmarking, technologies and methods of retention, adaptation, motivation, mentoring, and so on.

Forming a positive image of an educational organization, which includes the practice of adaptation, increases the productivity and competitiveness of the organization itself [13].

The rapid development of technology creates a new digital reality in human resource management. In the context of the transition to a digital economy and the transformation of

traditional classical organizations into digital ones, decentralization of digital management will take place on the basis of digital technologies. The most important characteristic feature of a digital organization is the interaction of the HR service with employees using mobile applications. Predictive HR analytics, employee-oriented professional training, and horizontal and vertical feedback require the development of new competencies of HR specialists [14].

Continuing to keep up with the times and use digital technologies, the HR department is transforming, automating some of its functions. Thus, according to the study *The Future of HR*, “during which more than one thousand heads of HR departments from 60 countries were interviewed, 2/3 of those surveyed see significant benefits of introducing digital technologies in HR. For more than three years, significant investments have been made by the heads of HR departments in predictive analytics, in improving solutions in process automation and in artificial intelligence” [15, p. 2].

V. A. Kapitanov, O. S. Osipova, L. S. Chikileva noted three main directions for the development of the HR service in the fight for talents: the necessary transition to digitalization to improve the competencies of the HR service of an educational organization; changed management, training and development of employees and organization of individual and collective project work; improving the results of developing an HR brand.

According to a Russian survey, respondents note that digitalization in HR is necessary:

- to get rid of the routine (71%);
- to improve access to the best labor resources using digital communication channels (46.7%);
- to develop remote forms of work (attracting staff from anywhere, at any time) (38.8%);
- to increase flexibility and individualization of personnel management (37.5%) [14].

Transformation of the HR service of an educational organization in the context of global digitalization will certainly require human and material costs. In various ways, a new financial model is needed. According to Diachkova and Kulkova [16, p. 88], the project-based financing model will be effective, assuming allocation of finance and other resources, including labor resources, to individual projects. Then the HR service will have greater mobility in choosing employees, and it will also be possible to generate job descriptions for employees for each project, which increases the certainty of the HR service work in a changing digital environment.

However, as the researchers note, the HR service is often itself a division of the company experiencing difficulties due to changes [17].

As Hans Paul Buerkner, Chairman of The Boston Consulting Group (BCG), rightly noted: “We believe that in order to return to the path of strong growth, Russia will have to completely revise not only its personnel but also its economic model, abandon the current illusion of stability and start working on creating an environment that will promote the development

and prosperity of talented professionals, or, as they are called today, “talents”. We see how the leading countries are actively transforming their educational systems, concentrating on the development of cognitive skills instead of the usual “load” of knowledge. They are actively involved in the retraining of the national workforce and help them adapt to a changing work environment by attracting the best professionals in the field of education and maximizing the opportunities of digitalization. We are confident that Russia needs to embark on the same path” [11].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the most promising strategic directions in the work of HR managers is the search inside and outside the educational organization, attracting and retaining talented employees. “In the most general sense, talent is a combination of a person’s abilities: his inherent talents, skills, knowledge, experience, intellect, prudence, character and energy. This also includes the ability to learn and grow” [18, p. 17]. At the same time, talent cannot be ignored, it is to be noticed and multiplied, since talented employees determine the success and competitiveness an educational organization will be having for years.

Attracting talented people should be an integral goal of any head of an educational organization, especially any head of HR service and any HR manager. Strengthening the team is a job that no leader is to delegate to anyone [18, p. 43]. At the same time, the search for talents needs constancy, without waiting for free vacancies, using digital technologies, active self-promotion, including on the Internet and social networks, attracting not only those who are looking for work but also those who are not currently looking for work. The search has to start in own team among long-standing teachers, setting own standards. Thus, in addition to assessing the effectiveness and potential of each teacher, the leader should be concerned about the satisfaction of each teacher with the psychological climate in the team, pleasure of communicating with colleagues, ability to solve personal problems, the level of claims and key questions for the leadership itself. Thus, talent management should become a priority in the work of the leader, fulfilling the role of strengthening the entire team of the organization.

Now talents strive for interesting tasks and wide opportunities for self-actualization and self-development. “They want to work for a great company with great leaders. They need an open, trusting and performance-oriented culture. Of course, they want significant opportunities for personal enrichment” [18, p. 44]. Great leadership and culture can be at the core of the greatest employee value proposition [18, p. 44]. It is impossible to create a universal value proposition for employees, unchanged for all time – these need to be refined either gradually or quickly and immediately, and this process should be ongoing and start with diagnostics.

Recently, most Russian leaders of large organizations began to gradually understand that their personal and activity characteristics should be supplemented with such skills as attracting, retaining, and developing talents.

The managerial characteristics of a modern leader of a large organization are “a combination of a sharp strategic mind, leadership abilities, emotional maturity, communication skills, entrepreneurial instincts, functional skills, the ability to achieve results, as well as the ability to attract and inspire other talents” [18, p. 17]. All this also applies to modern leaders of educational organizations, who are to certainly take care of the issue of managing talented employees. “...The question of talent management should not just be on the agenda of the top management of every company – it should be the first priority!” [18, p. 10]. Undoubtedly, the most talented employees (both teachers of educational organizations and management personnel) contribute to the success of the organization, yet numerous managers do not pay enough attention to this issue.

Another key issue of the HR service is not just to improve personnel processes but to select and place leaders in the organization [18, p. 14].

In the struggle for talented employees, one of the weighty arguments can be a value proposition for employees based on professional leadership and a corporate “culture of the heart”, including at least: “absence of harassment, manipulation, secrecy, deceit, duplicity” [18, p. 90]. Such a value proposition should also include the ability to communicate with other employees.

Since there will be less and less talented effective managers in any field every year, the war for talent will only intensify. The brainstorming methodology for finding new talent needs to be strengthened with completely new aspects that are different from the traditional characteristics of candidates, and consider, among other things, other education, career stages, places and work experience, demographics [18, p. 125].

As soon as the head of the company understands the relevance of the war for talent, this will immediately increase both the efficiency of the head himself and the effective work of the organization. This war can only be won by rebuilding and implementing all the components of a new recruitment strategy, such as: an ongoing talent hunt, introduction of talented specialists at all levels, identification of employees who are passively looking for work, use of various sources of search, changes in the rules for additional remuneration, and others [18, p. 108].

To increase the efficiency of the organization and to bring it to a leading position, it is necessary to change the recruitment strategy. The new recruitment strategy, in addition to selecting, educating and adapting new employees, should include a developed benchmark for evaluating candidates for vacant positions. An educational organization “is to constantly hunt for talents in order to attract them just when they are ready to change jobs” [18, p.

118]. For this, another successful method of situational recruitment is employed – newly hired employees from other areas (business, military, etc.) are accepted into transitional positions, in which they are participating (from six months to one and a half years) in certain projects of the organization, performing internal audits or other work. At the end of this period, the employee is either accepted for a permanent position or leaves altogether; this is what General Electric, the leader in this strategy, does [18, p. 120].

Beginners bring in a new way of looking at things, their talents and creativity. The conditions for the display of creative abilities are: “a strong and stable need for creativity, general intellectual and special abilities, enthusiasm for the task being performed, creative fantasy and imagination” [19, p. 89]. Creativity, in turn, is a synthesis of the natural development of the potential and creative activity of a person with the unconscious and conscious, random and non-random [20, p. 1295]. The experience of building a team with people of different backgrounds and levels, with creative abilities, different thinking, experience, methods of solving problems and situations strengthens any organization [18, p. 123–124].

Numerous company executives are convinced of the special importance of attracting candidates based on their personal qualities and not on experience and knowledge. The founder of Visa, Dee Hock, argued: “Hire and promote, first, on the basis of honesty; second, motivation; third, abilities; fourth, understanding; fifth, knowledge; and only last on the basis of experience. Without honesty, motivation is dangerous; without motivation, abilities cannot be applied; without ability, understanding is limited; without understanding knowledge is useless; without knowledge, experience is blind. People who have all these qualities, except for experience, will easily acquire it and quickly find a worthy use for it” [18, p. 124]. Employers need to look for candidates who can easily adapt to the culture of an educational organization, and not initially correspond to it, those who can enrich this culture, bring their own vision.

The HR system is distinguished by its commitment to the so-called “paper” technologies; they work independently and are not built into any other business functions, forming an impression that the HR sphere would not be changed by digital technologies. HR specialists note that the most promising areas for automating their functions are personnel administration, recruitment, compensation calculation and staff training [15, p. 2].

To search for talented candidates, organizations are actively using digital technologies and Internet resources.

In this age, IT-technologies significantly save time and reduce labor costs in multiple areas. “Specially designed applications can automatically retrieve resumes, administer screening tests for candidates, check their education and experience, schedule interviews, keep in touch with the candidate, share resumes with other departments, and generate reports” [18, p. 126].

The use of digital HR methods allows for a “point search” for teaching staff and management personnel that most fully meets the requirements. The prospect of introducing HR technologies lies in the optimization and automation of routine processes. For example, compiling electronic resume forms, filtering and sorting them, creating and storing a database of candidates for vacancies, etc., reduces the loss of time and enables the HR manager to pay more attention to the quality of selected candidates for emerging vacancies.

The transition from a traditional organization to a digital organization, according to 56.6% of respondents, will affect the work of HR managers to change the qualification requirements for HR specialists. Every fourth respondent believes that the role of the personnel service will increase, the institution of personnel business partnership will not lose its significance, and strategic thinking will become the main competence of an internal HR manager (24.3%) [14]. A significant proportion of respondents advocate the acquisition/development of fundamentally new competencies, including the development of skills such as digital design in HR and employee emotion management. Interviewed HR professionals expressed a desire to develop digital creativity, a personal digital profile, and develop digital empathy.

Another way to successfully hunt for talent, which allows an educational organization to become a leader in the struggle for efficiency and competitiveness in the educational services market, is to build and constantly update its own database.

The database of candidates includes everyone who has ever been associated with this organization:

- candidates who did not accept the offer of cooperation in due time;
- acquaintances and friends of current employees;
- talented employees who left the educational organization;
- employees of other departments of the organization, not quite successfully working there but suitable for work in other structural divisions;
- most effective, active and talented employees of third-party competing organizations;
- graduate students of schools and colleges, actively participating in competitions and winning awards;
- active participants in industry conferences [18, p. 127].

Moreover, constant contact is required with all potential candidates; materials about the news and ongoing events in the educational organization and invitations are to be sent, and access to the organization’s website with information of interest to the candidate is needed – all this builds a relationship of trust and nourishes the feeling of being always welcome for an interview and for work in this particular organization [18, p. 127-128].

Yet the leading position in the hunt for talent is occupied by personal connections. Even though almost 40% of talents were hired through acquaintances and recommended by

employees of the organization, only a small number of organizations wisely use this colossal resource of connections of their employees [18, p. 129]. Therefore, it is necessary to involve all employees of the educational organization in the work on creating a database, each of which is to participate in conferences, chats, Internet mailing lists, all kinds of associations, building their own network of talented candidates [18, p. 129–130]. Naturally, the leadership of the educational organization should provide material rewards for this constant work on the search for talents.

Organizations show great ingenuity in this field – for instance, eighty employees, together with the management, held a two-day telethon to which they invited the potential candidates, and another organization recruited talented programmers through a video game posted on its website. Those who scored the most points became candidates for vacancies. Another organization that was recruiting for the IT department held a competition for hackers to break into their system, and those who showed the most creative approach were invited to work [18, p. 130].

Another important aspect in the war for talent is when the process of hiring a candidate turns from selection into persuasion. Moreover, for persuasion, the most effective and talented employees should be delegated, and after each interview with presentations, the candidate would have a strong desire to work in this particular educational organization. The best employees set the required level of talent, which determines the level of achievement of the entire organization. Often, in the final decision to fill a vacancy, according to top managers, the presence of the head of the organization is necessary. Thus, professionals and key managers are to carefully organize the entire process of hiring candidates.

Together with the head of the educational organization and the HR department, it is necessary to design a recruitment strategy to “introduce talent at all levels, constantly hunt for them, use different sources, be creative in developing new channels, break compensation rules when necessary, and be able to convince the right people to be candidates for you” [18, p. 135].

Adaptation is an important psychological element in a talent retention strategy. There are no universal best practices for effective adaptation for all organizations – “one good practice does not fit all companies”. Socio-professional adaptation should include a whole range of activities for socialization and harmonious entry into the team, but, sometimes, as part of adaptation, a “buddy” is assigned to the newcomer to watch over them at first [13]. The authors of the present study beg to differ – to retain a talented employee, a “chaperon” appointed for a short time, who simply introduces the structure of the company, reminds of a particular event, etc., is not needed – it should be a professional mentor who is able to accompany the employee for a long time, sufficient for full adaptation in the team.

Mentorship is a critical item in the war for talent and retention. The general aspects of mentoring are:

- mentoring is recommended to be included in the schedule of mentors;
- mentors should meet with their students at least once a month;
- management defines topics for discussion between the mentor and the student;
- confidentiality rules are mandatory;
- the organization establishes the main provisions of the mentoring rating;
- rewards for mentoring are determined [18, p. 165-166].

The mentor should emphasize the importance of the organization to each student and communicate with them regularly to keep abreast of their progress. At the same time, both parties should take responsibility for the communication process in mentoring [18, p. 166].

Organizations may run multiple mentoring programs at the same time. Moreover, such programs can have different plans, duration and start at different times. An effective mentoring program is run by Arrow's IT division. When selecting a mentor-student pair, the organizing committee collects detailed information about the student candidate, including goals, objectives, development needs, and expectations from the program. Thus, twice a year the organizing committee promotes the formation of 10-15 mentor-student pairs [18, p. 166].

Such programs provide an opportunity to maintain effective communication with key employees and senior managers of a large team around the world and join the values and philosophy of the company. This process is mutually beneficial, because together with the satisfaction of developmental needs, the student also grows emotional attachment to the company, so they do not even think about leaving it, and the mentor is encouraged for active mentoring [18, p. 167].

For a convincing victory in the war for talents, the leaders of an educational organization are to develop the abilities of their employees, improving achievements and personal qualities through various tasks, material incentives and support. Numerous employees emphasize the importance of assignments, justified criticism in case of failure, and a new responsible task, which does not allow them to dwell on their mistakes [18, p. 139].

To unlock the potential of all employees, it is necessary to build a new approach to development into the organization itself – it can be difficult and interesting work, coaching, assessment, individual mentoring for everyone and support [18, p. 141]. For the qualitative development of talented employees, mentors require a lot of emotional and time costs and personal involvement; they are to be able to see the potential and unique abilities of their wards [18, p. 143].

Talented employees need not only to expand their responsibilities but also to change them and switch to other responsibilities; they need to be confronted with unusual complex tasks that they have not yet encountered. Special development tasks include:

1. Development of projects from scratch.
2. Changing the duties of a line manager to administrative duties.
3. Solving problems in problem areas [18, p. 145].

Some organizations take risks by promoting young people who are ready for a career jump to leadership positions [18, p. 145-146]. At the same time, they are to be ready to provide talents with constant mentoring, assessment, and coaching [18, p. 146].

CONCLUSION

Global digitalization and the war for talent are the latest stage in the development of the HR service of a modern educational organization, which imposes new requirements on the competency model of HR specialists. Scientists are developing a new technology of personnel competencies for Industry 4.0.

Taking into account the promising directions of global digitalization and strategic planning, the HR service of an educational organization should become a fundamental structure and an active tool in management, strategic development, building effective work to achieve the organization's global goals, and work to realize its mission. The HR service of an educational organization is to quickly respond to the challenges of the time, skillfully master the methods and tools of the war for talents and become a forge of talents. Besides, the HR service is to constantly expand the quality of services in talent management, increase their competence, efficiency, motivate, accompany continuous education, work steadily on the value proposition for employees.

In this regard, it is necessary to improve the system of advanced training and retraining of HR employees and to develop a competency model for an HR manager of an educational organization within the framework of a competency-based approach.

REFERENCES

1. Lektorsky, V. A. (2022). Global digitalization as an anthropological challenge. Man and artificial intelligence systems. Ed. V. A. Lektorsky. St. Petersburg: Publishing House "Legal Center", 18–29.
2. Federal project "Digital educational environment". Available at: <https://edu.gov.ru/national-project/projects/cos/> (accessed: 02/12/2022).
3. Federal project "Modern school". Available at: <https://edu.gov.ru/national-project/>

- projects/school/ (accessed: 02/12/2022).
4. National project "Education". Project development plan. Available at: <https://edu.gov.ru/national-project/plan/> (accessed: 02/15/2022).
 5. Lykova, O. A., & Petrukhin, A. A. (2019). Formation of the HR service management system in the organization. Economics and management: current trends. Digest of articles. Cheboksary: Sreda Publishing House.
 6. Pochachalov, E. S. (2019). Features of interaction between line managers and HR managers at Russian enterprises. Achievements and prospects for the development of youth science. Collection of articles of the International scientific-practical conference. *Petrozavodsk: New Science*, 237–240.
 7. Shahreki, J. (2022). High-performance work systems and HR efficiency The mediating role of HRIS potentialities. *International Journal of Management and Decision Making*. DOI: 10.1504/IJMDM.2024.10052704.
 8. Zherebtsova, O. B. (2016). Modern personnel service in an educational organization. *Eurasian Union of Scientists (ESU)*, 5 (26).
 9. Nizovaya, E. V. (2018). Trends in innovative approaches to the organization's personnel management at the present stage of development. *Management of organizations in the modern economy: theory and technology. Collection of scientific works of the All-Russian scientific-practical conference*. Kemerovo, KGU Publ.
 10. Richenhagen, G., JESSL, R., Maya, F., & Raimund, W. (2021). HR Service Experience 2021. Publisher: Haufe Verlag, Freiburg. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354750245> (accessed: 16.02.2022).
 11. Russia 2025: from personnel to talents. Research materials of The Boston Consulting Group (in partnership with Sberbank PJSC, Contribution to the Future Charitable Foundation, Worldskills Union and Global Education Futures) / The Boston Consulting Group, Inc., 2017, 72. Available at: <https://vbudushee.ru/library/rossiya-2025-ot-kadrov-k-talantam/> (accessed: 02/17/2022).
 12. Alieva, E. N., & Makarenko, O. S. (2020). Motivation of work of pedagogical workers. *Complex and sectoral problems of science and ways to solve them. Collection of articles of the International scientific-practical conference*. Ufa, Aeterna Publ., 111–112.
 13. Krugielka, A., Bartkowiak, G., Knap-Stefaniuk, A., Sowa-Behtane, E., & Dachowski, R. (2023). Onboarding in Polish Enterprises in the Perspective of HR Specialists. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20, 1512. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph20021512
 14. Kapitanov, V. A., Osipova, O. S., & Chikileva, L. S. (2021). Promising Areas for Developing HR Managers' Competencies in the Digital Age, 01. DOI: 10.1051/

shsconf/20219101016.

15. Kolesnikova, Yu. A., & Safarli, M. S. (2021). Digitalization of HR processes: analysis and systematization of the experience of using tools. *Modern Science*, 1–2, 57–65.
16. Diachkova, A. V., & Kulkova, L. I. (2019). Financing an educational institution: the search for an optimal business model. *Modern problems of science and education*, 2, 85–93.
17. Blume, P. (2006). HR Service Delivery Maturity Model. *Human Capital Management*, 01. DOI: 10.1007/3-540-33299-5_5.
18. Michaels, E., Handfield-Jones, X., & Axelrod, E. (2005). War for talent / trans. from English. Yu. E. Kornilovich. Moscow, Mann, Ivanov and Ferber Publ.
19. Tomyuk, O. N. (2013). Creativity: ontological aspect. *Epistemes: a collection of scientific articles*. Issue. 8: Problems of modern ontology. Ekaterinburg, Azhur Publ., 82–90.
20. Tomyuk, O. N. (2014). Creativity and Lawmaking: Ontological Aspect. *Journal of Siberian Federal University. Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7, 8, 1293–1300.

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